

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

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1. Summary

The CYCLOPES project intends to create and preserve an innovation-driven network of Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) battling cybercrime, enhancing the EU's capabilities to combat growing cyber threats. With innovation at the core of LEA's operations, a new discussion begins regarding how all this innovation will be managed. Innovation uptake expresses that process and consists of four major concepts: identifying the specific needs of users, using the best innovative procurement model for the job, ensuring the greatest impact of a new innovation and finally, validation of the innovation. In this document, existing frameworks, best practices and other related activities are gathered in an attempt to guide this process of Innovation Uptake. This is the first report of five that will be updated as the project progresses.

2. Introduction

Innovation is a new or improved product or process (or a combination thereof) that differs significantly from the unit's previous products or processes and that has been made available to potential users (product) or brought into use by the unit (process). Individuals, institutions, entire economic sectors, and countries can all benefit from innovation as it is central to the improvements in living standards [1]. Innovations derive from knowledge-based activities that involve the practical application of existing or newly developed information and knowledge. Information consists of organized data and can be reproduced and transferred across organizations at a low cost. Knowledge refers to an understanding of information and the ability to use the information for different purposes. Knowledge is obtained through cognitive effort and consequently, new knowledge is difficult to transfer because it requires learning on the part of the recipient. Both information and knowledge can be sourced or created within or outside a relevant organization.

2.1. Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is organized as follows:

- Section 3 offers a better understanding of innovation. It describes the main activities of innovation as well as activities that are not considered innovation, in an attempt to help clarify what innovation is and isn't.
- Section 4 demonstrates the innovation framework that will be developed in the CYCLOPES project.
- Section 5 displays the existing current frameworks for Innovation Uptake.
- Section 6 demonstrates the Identified Innovation Procurement experiences across EUROPE in the area of Security
- Section 7 reveals the innovation Uptake action that is planned for the Cyclopes project.

3. Understanding Innovation

3.1. Main Innovation Activities

The main eight types of activities that organizations undertake in pursuit of innovation are displayed below [2] while many of these mostly knowledge-based activities can also be used for other, more general goals.

Figure 1 Main Innovation Activities

Research and experimental development activities

Research and experimental development (R&D) is a creative and systematic process that aims to expand the stock of information and develop new uses for that knowledge. Applied research, by definition, is focused on a specific practical goal or target, whereas experimental development aims to create new goods or processes or improve current ones. As a result, there is a desire to innovate.

Engineering, design, and other creative work activities

Engineering, design and other creative work encompass experimental and creative activities that are connected to R&D but do not fit all five R&D criteria. These activities include R&D follow-up or auxiliary activities, as well as activities carried out independently of R&D.

Marketing and brand equity activities

Market research and market testing, pricing, product placement, and promotion; product advertising, product promotion at trade shows or exhibits, and the formulation of marketing strategies are all examples of marketing and brand equity operations. They also include public relations operations that contribute to a firm's reputation and brand equity, as well as advertising for trademarks that are not directly related to a specific product, such as advertising linked to the firm's name. Marketing and brand equity initiatives do not include sales and distribution.

Intellectual property-related activities

The protection and commercialization of knowledge, which is typically developed through R&D, software development, engineering, design, and other creative activity, are examples of IP-related activities. All administrative and legal work to apply for, register, document, manage, trade, license-out, market, and enforce a firm's intellectual property rights (IPRs), as well as all activities to acquire IPRs from other organizations, such as licensing-in or outright purchase of IP, and activities to sell IP to third parties, fall under the category of IP activities. Patents, utility patents, industrial designs, trademarks, copyright, integrated circuit designs, plant breeder's rights (new plant varieties), geographical indications, and confidential information such as trade secrets are all examples of intellectual property rights (IPRs).

Employee training activities

Employee training refers to all activities that are paid for or subsidized by the company for employees to gain the information and skills needed for their specific trade, occupation, or job. On-the-job training and job-related education at training and educational institutions are examples of employee training.

Software development and database activities

When used to build new or enhanced business processes or products, such as computer games, logistical systems, or software to integrate corporate operations, software development is considered an innovation activity. When used for innovation, such as studies of data on material qualities or customer preferences, database operations are considered an innovation activity.

Activities related to the acquisition or lease of tangible assets

These operations include the purchase, leasing, or acquisition of buildings, machinery, and equipment through a takeover, as well as the in-house manufacturing of such commodities for personal use. Instruments, transportation equipment, and computer hardware for IT systems are examples of equipment. The firm's tangible assets are kept on the balance sheets for more than a year. In national accounts, the acquisition of tangible assets falls under the category of gross fixed capital formation for the relevant asset categories. The financial statements of a company will show expenditures on property, plant, and equipment additions. The overall worth of the stock of assets will be reflected in the balance sheets. Firms can protect their services by leasing or renting them from other parties in addition to purchasing or creating them on their own. Payments for cloud services to use assets such as servers are included. These charges might be thought of as an indirect measure of usage.

Innovation management

All systematic actions to plan, administer, and control internal and external resources for innovation are included in innovation management. This includes how resources for innovation are allocated, how responsibilities and decision-making are organized among employees, how collaboration with external partners is managed, how external inputs are integrated into a firm's innovation activities, and how activities to monitor innovation results and support learning from experience are carried out. Activities for defining policies, goals, objectives, procedures, structures, roles, and responsibilities for dealing with innovation in the firm, as well as systems to assess and review them, are all part of innovation management. Information on innovation management is useful for studies looking at the effectiveness of spending on innovation activities in terms of generating sales or other innovation results (see Chapter 5 for further details on innovation management).

3.2. Changes that are not Innovations

This section discusses changes that are either not an innovation or which can only be considered an innovation if specific conditions are met. The basic principle is that innovation must have been implemented and must be significantly different from the organization's previous products or processes.

- Routine modifications or upgrades do not constitute product innovation in and of itself. This applies to software updates that merely detect and correct coding flaws.
- Replacing or extending existing capital is not an innovation. Purchases of identical models of installed equipment, as well as small extensions and modifications to existing equipment or software, fall under this category. New equipment or expansions must be brand new to the company and represent a considerable improvement in specifications.
- Product introductions that merely entail modest aesthetic alterations, such as a color change or a slight shape change, do not meet the "substantial difference" standard and are hence not product innovations.
- Companies that specialize in bespoke manufacturing and create one-of-a-kind, typically complex goods or services in response to a customer's request. It is not a product innovation unless the one-off item has significant differences from previous products created by the company.
- Product innovation is generally not a concept, prototype, or model of a product that does not yet exist because it does not match the implementation criteria.
- The outputs of creative and professional service firms, such as client reports, novels, and films, are not always innovative for the companies that create them. For example, a report by a consulting firm summarizing the findings of a design project completed under contract for a customer without key novelty components is not a product innovation for the consulting business.

4. Innovation Framework

The Innovation Framework consists of four steps. The first step, Acquisition, focuses on how to search for innovation from various sources such as Universities, government organizations for security, databases, Projects Funded by the European Commission, and companies. Secondly, the innovation gathered must be implemented and tested. This is achieved through the definition of testbeds, datasets Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for technology, and previously defined success criteria. In the second step, Implementation, the testbed, datasets, success criteria, or KPI for technology are defined. In the third stage, Validation, a technology readiness level [2] of TRL8 is necessary which is defined as a system being complete and qualified. It is important to keep in mind that regardless of the technology being complete and qualified mistakes can happen Finally, in the last step of Improvement a Technology Readiness Level TRL9 is required. This is defined as an actual system proven in an operational environment.

Figure 2 Innovation Framework

4.1. Acquisition

Research and experimental development (R&D) are one of a range of activities that can generate innovations, or through which useful knowledge for innovation can be acquired. Other methods of gaining potentially useful knowledge include market research, engineering activities to assess the efficiency of processes, or analyzing data from the users of digital goods or services. Innovation-relevant information can be gathered without a specific application in mind, for instance, to help develop and evaluate options for future actions.

4.2. Implementation

For a new idea, model, method, or prototype to be considered an innovation, it needs to be implemented. Implementation requires organizations to make systematic efforts to ensure that the innovation is accessible to potential users, either for the organization's processes and procedures or to external users for its products. The requirement for implementation is a defining characteristic of innovation that distinguishes it from inventions, prototypes, new ideas, etc. At a minimum, innovations must contain characteristics that were not previously made available by the relevant organization to its users. An important aspect of innovation that is worth mentioning is the diffusion of information which explains the rate at which new ideas and technology spread and the rate at which first responders are likely to adapt to new technology.

4.3. Validation

Value is an implicit goal of innovation that evolves to provide different types of benefits to different stakeholders. However, the realization of the value of an innovation is uncertain and can only be fully assessed sometime after its implementation. Value-related measures are important for understanding the impacts of innovation. Complementary measures and analytical strategies can be used to trace innovation outcomes after a suitable length of time. The importance of outcome measures depends on the intended uses of innovation data. They are particularly necessary for the study of government policy initiatives to promote innovation that delivers socially desirable outcomes such as inclusion, sustainability, jobs, or economic growth. Although value is an implicit goal of innovation that cannot be guaranteed because innovation outcomes are uncertain and heterogeneous.

4.4. Improvement

Follow-on activities to review innovations after their implementation can result in minor improvements or radical innovations, e.g. through a fundamental redesign or major improvements. Some of these follow-on efforts could potentially result in innovations in their own right. Post-implementation reviews can also lead to the abandonment of innovations.

5. Current Frameworks

5.1. PCP

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) [4] refers to the procurement of research and development of new innovative solutions before they are commercially available. In this method, different suppliers competing through different phases of development. Moreover, procurers and suppliers share the risks and benefits under market conditions. This risk-benefit sharing is related to the IPRs resulting from the research and development (R&D) with suppliers at market price. The competitive approach used in PCP is known as the competitive development where procurers buy the R&D from several competing R&D providers and then compare and identify the best value for money solutions available to address the PCP challenges. R&D is split into phases (solution design, prototyping, original development, and validation/testing of the first products) with the number of competing R&D providers being reduced after each evaluation phase.

The European Commission supports PCP for multiple reasons. Firstly, it enables public procurers to share the risks and benefits of designing, prototyping, and testing new products and services with the suppliers. Moreover, it helps create optimum conditions for the wide commercialization and take-up of the results of R&D. In addition, it assists in the development of innovative solutions for the societal challenges of the future. It also encourages companies to invest in highly qualified R&D in Europe. Finally, it acts as a "seal of approval" confirming the market potential of new emerging technological developments, thereby attracting new investors. The most important aspect of PCP is that it supports the creation of a strong European market for innovative products and services. This approach encourages European public authorities to innovate upon the provision of public services faster and it further creates opportunities for companies in Europe to take international leadership within new markets.

Since 2009, the Commission has launched calls for proposals to support the establishment of networks of public authorities on PCP, thus raising awareness by the sharing of best practices. Moreover, cooperation is encouraged among public procurers from the different Member States. This results in jointly implemented pre-commercial procurements. Since 2012, the Commission has gone even further by co-financing pan-European consortia of public procurers who wish to undertake pre-commercial procurement together on topics of common European interest. This support is being extended under Horizon 2020, with financial incentives such as the PCP Co-Fund actions available for consortia of public procurers working together on joint PCPs within the domain of research and innovation defined under each different program.

5.2. PPI

Public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI) [5] occurs when the public sector uses its purchasing power to act as an early adopter of innovative solutions which are not yet available on a large-scale commercial basis. To give incentive to the industry to invest in wide commercialization and bring innovative solutions to the market, PPI provides large enough demand, with the quality and price needed for mass-market deployment. This then enables the public sector to modernize public services with better value for money solutions and provides growth opportunities for companies.

Initially, it is essential to create a critical mass of purchasing power on the demand side. This can be achieved by finding one large buyer or several smaller buyers in a buyers' group. The selection of the buyer has the power to incentivize the industry to scale up the production and bring solutions to the market with the price and quality requirements for large-scale deployment. In the second step, the procurer states the innovation needs to take into account the required functionality/performance and possibly also price requirements. The last step is the actual public procurement of the innovative solutions through one of the existing public procurement procedures, such as an open/negotiated procedure, competitive dialogue, etc.

PPI is thus complementary to Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), as PPI can enable larger-scale deployment of solutions that were developed in small quantities in a preceding PCP. PPI can also be used independently, to bring to the market innovative solutions that do not result from R&D but for example from organizational or process innovation. PPI has significant advantages as it helps create demand for innovative solutions through government procurement. With PPI is possible to modernize public services with higher quality and more cost-efficient solutions. Moreover, by boosting a particular new market for innovative solutions, it helps innovative companies reach economies of scale to grow their business.

5.3. Innovation Procurement

Innovation procurement [6] focuses on the development of innovative solutions through the procurement of research and development services. This approach also includes the procurement of innovative solutions that are not yet available or do not exist on the market as well as the procurement of innovative solutions that do exist but are not yet widely available on the market. With this methodology The European Commission aims to improve public procurement practices, promote the demand for innovative goods, services and works in Europe, and foster the uptake of innovation in the EU, thus allowing the integration of public demand into the innovation ecosystem and the fostering of economic recovery.

There is a wide range of advantages in the public procurement of innovation. For instance, public buyers can shape markets and create new markets as well as increase the quality of public services and boost smart investments. In addition, it can assist in fostering the market uptake of innovative products, services, and works as well as support access to markets for businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This can have a large positive impact on mobility, health, education, etc. due to the high volume of public spending

The European Commission promotes innovation procurement by supporting public buyers looking to develop or purchase innovative solutions by guiding innovation procurement, including practical information on how to start and develop procurement of innovation projects. Moreover, it offers webinars and podcasts to improve procurement professionalization on strategic issues. The European Union also finances innovation procurement projects aimed at developing more innovation-oriented practices that contribute to smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth thus stimulating the development of innovative enterprises in Europe.

6. Identified Innovation Procurement across EUROPE in the area of Security

Innovation Procurement is generating increasing interest in recent years. The European Commission believes that sourcing innovation will help the European Union's economic recovery after the corona crisis. In addition, Innovation Procurement can also contribute to the transition to a sustainable digital federation. To provide public procurement officials with tools and encourage innovative procurement, the European Commission presented innovative procurement guidelines on 18 June 2021 [8].

In this deliverable, a thorough scan was conducted to identify all innovation procurement projects in the area of security, funded so far by Horizon 2020 Programme. These projects are significant to the CYCLOPES Project as they provide a stepping-stone where frameworks for innovation uptake procedures have already been put into practice, thus the CYCLOPES consortium can base its work by building on previous efforts on the same topic of Innovation Uptake from any public or private practitioner.

In the project's first year, priority was given to creating a landscape of European innovation projects in the area of security, accordingly, the CYCLOPES consortium gathered the proposed projects below. The landscape created, is of grave importance to building the foundation of the future Innovation uptake efforts within the project that will be discussed in the upcoming deliverables. Moreover, it is essential to state that while there are other active efforts in the area of innovation uptake, only projects funded by the EU are of interest, as the scope of innovation uptake in this deliverable is limited within the European Innovation.

More specifically innovation procurement focuses on the development of innovative solutions, the procurement of innovative solutions that are not yet available or do not exist on the market and finally the procurement of innovative solutions that do exist but are not yet widely available on the market. Through the public procurement of innovation, public buyers as in the case of LEAs for CYCLOPES project can shape the market of tools supporting LEAs in fighting cybercrime; foster market uptake of innovative solutions and services; increase the quality of their fighting cybercrime knowhow; boost smart investment in innovative and useful tools; implement innovation, technologies and modernizing public sector.

Specifically, CYCLOPES consortium intends to follow the framework currently used for innovation procurements [3] which challenges industry from the demand side for innovative solutions for public sector needs: Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and Public Procurement of Innovative solution (PPI) as a roadmap to Innovation uptake from public practitioner / tenderer. Specifically, all projects are following the structured forms of innovation uptake.

Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) can be used by procurers when there are no near-to-the-market solutions yet. Thus, the PCP approach is suggested here for solutions that according to market research and CYCLOPES results have low TRL<=6, however they have desirable and unique features that are selected by LEAs during CYCLOPES workshops. The PCP can therefore be used to compare the pros and cons of alternative solutions approaches and de-risk the promising innovations. Also, PCP is a public procurement of R&D services that does not include the deployment of commercial volumes of end-products, thus research-oriented fighting cybercrime solutions can be also channeled towards their uptake/adoption by LEAs which will be otherwise not be possible through conventional market routs.

Public Procurement of Innovative solutions (PPI) to address challenges of public interest by innovative solutions that are nearly or already in small quantity on the market. PPI framework can thus be used when there is no need for procurement of new R&D to bring solutions to the market, but a clear signal from a sizeable amount of early adopters/launch customers that they are willing to purchase/deploy the innovative solutions, as in this case LEAs interested fighting cybercrime tools with TRL higher than TRL7. PPIs involve also conformance testing before deployment (TRL8 and 9). Collectively, PPIs is can offer a smooth transition from market research of Cybersecurity tools and Workshops for introducing these tools to LEAs performed during CYCLOPES project to actual marketization of the most prominent solutions (not in the market with high TRL >7) or uptake existing solutions (market ready TRL9) that fit best LEAs needs.

All the below mentioned projects bring value to the CYCLOPES Project with the creation of guidelines, publications, platforms, procurement experts, best practices and lessons learned.

6.1. BroadMap

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Mapping Interoperable EU PPDR Broadband Communication Applications and Technology		http://www.broadmap.eu/	1 May 2016 – 30 April 2027

Objective

The BROADMAP project will take the first steps towards future procurement of ‘interoperable next generation of broadband radio communication systems for public safety and security’ (DRS-18) to improve PPDR’s service to Europe’s citizens and enhance interoperability across borders.

The primary goal of this project is to collect and validate the PPDR (Public Protection and Disaster Relief) organisations’ existing requirements with the aim to establish a core set of specifications, and roadmap for procurement, to achieve future evolution of EU broadband applications and interoperable radio communication solutions

This project implements a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) with the purpose to inform and guide the future procurement of research and development, networks and devices and their deployment to realise new interoperable broadband networks, and the ecosystems of applications and services to support the PPDR and critical communications community.

Project BROADMAP addresses the following goals:

- to collect, assess and validate the PPDR’s wireless broadband communication requirements;
- to establish a core set of specifications to fulfil the requirements;
- to define transition roadmaps for research and standardisation for future evolution of European interoperable radio communication solutions, within legal procurement constraints;
- to prepare the ground for a new eco-system to catalyse new applications, services and processes making use of broadband capabilities for public safety and security;
- to utilise the strength of the PPDR community through our partners, their expertise, knowledge, networks and relations with the aim to achieving interoperability across Europe. This importantly includes nuances of societal differences, including different cultures, geography, processes and legal frameworks

BROADMAP integrates 15 potential buyers/end users from 15 countries, 8 of which are responsible ministries. 48 further end users provide initial support.

Relevance to Cyclopes Project

BroadMap (Mapping Interoperable EU PPDR Broadband Communication Applications and Technology) is an ongoing project, whose efforts and outcomes will be used in later Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) actions, and/or Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI), which may be subject of subsequent projects funded by European Council. Similarly, to CYCLOPES the BroadMap Project will collect and validate existing requirements to establish a core set of specifications and roadmap for procurement. Broadmap is focusing on achieving the future evolution of EU broadband applications and interoperable radio communication solutions. Even though CYCLOPES is technology unrelated to BroadMap, the procurement procedures can provide a framework to the CYCLOPES Consortium to achieve EU innovation uptake of best practices for Cybercrime.

6.2. BroadWay

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
<p>Innovation activity to develop technologies to enable a pan-European interoperable broadband mobile system for PPDR, validated by sustainable testing facilities</p>		<p>https://www.broadway-info.eu/</p>	<p>1 May 2018 – 30 September 2022</p>
Objective			
<p>BroadWay will take the first procurement steps to enable 'interoperable next generation of broadband radio communication systems for public safety and security' to improve Public Safety and Disaster relief organisation's (PPDR's) service to Europe's citizens, and enhance interoperability across borders.</p> <p>The primary goal of this project is to: 'Procure Innovation activity to develop and demonstrate TRL8 technologies that will enable a pan-European interoperable broadband mobile system for PPDR, validated by sustainable testing facilities'. This project implements a Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) with the purpose to realise innovative solutions for the implementation of the 'SpiceNet Reference' architecture as defined by the BroadMap project. A pan-European pilot system will be developed within the timeframe 2021, validated by sustainable test capabilities, and to the satisfaction of a European wide team of public safety practitioners. The BroadWay team, plus this additional support, covers a total of 23 European Countries with 7 additional countries represented by their ministries responsible for public safety communication.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>BroadWay (Innovation activity to develop technologies to enable a pan-European interoperable broadband mobile system for Public Protection and Disaster Relief) took the first procurement steps to enable and implement Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and can be seen as an important study case for the CYCLOPES Projects as it will be finalized within 2022. The Cyclopes project needs to refer to how other projects have handled PCP in order to continue the previous work conducted and innovate on that.</p>			

6.3. CIVILnEXt

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Next generation of information systems to support EU external policies		https://www.civilnext.eu/	1 May 2018 – 30 April 2022
Objective			
<p>The main objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop the OCP through an innovative modular design concept to respond to the diverse needs and contexts of civilian CSDP missions in a cost-effective and interoperable way. • Work with and build upon existing information management systems and initiatives that are in place in the context of civilian CSDP and wider EU external action. • Cooperate with the Mission Support Platform (MSP) to underpin and support the development of the future OCP. • Design the OCP not for the users but with the users, following an interactive design, prototyping and operational validation process that results in the documentation, testing and validation of the use of the Platform in two operational scenarios in the Southern EU Neighbourhood and/or Africa and in the Eastern EU Neighbourhood (including the Western Balkans). • Ensure institutional facilitation for the broad range and the complexity of civilian CSDP to underpin smart specialization and market uptake of the OCP through further procurements and synergies between FPI, ESIF and H2020 funding (PPI) at EU level. 			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>CIVILnEXt (Next generation of information systems to support EU external policies) aims to improve coordination in EU external action through better information exchange, situational awareness, and operation control in diverse theaters of operation. CIVILnEXt engages the participation of four national competent authorities, active in EU external policies and the UN organizations IOM. Similarly, CYCLOPES brings together organizations such as EUROPOL, EACTDA, ECTEG, ENLETS, i-LEAD that will inevitably become beneficiaries of procurement results in their attempt to work together and in combating threats posed by cybercrime.</p>			

6.4. SHUTTLE

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Scientific High-throughput and Unified Toolkit for Trace analysis by forensic Laboratories in Europe		https://www.shuttle-pcp.eu/	1 May 2018 – 30 April 2022
Objective			
<p>SHUTTLE will automate a significant part of forensic microtrace evidence examinations. The SHUTTLE toolkit will mainly consist of an automated microscope that will acquire high quality images of recovered microtraces. Images will be processed automatically and an overview of available microtraces will be reported. In the first instance, we will focus on blood, skin cells, gunshot residues (especially NC), hairs, fibres and saliva. Algorithms to classify additional microtraces, or to classify microtraces more accurately, can be developed by users and added as plug-ins to extend the range of microtraces that can be classified. The data will be stored in a computer database, thereby facilitating future data analysis, such as the provenance of microtraces and forensic comparisons.</p> <p>SHUTTLE aims to solve two major issues in forensic microtrace evidence investigation.</p> <p>First, current analyses are subjective and require a high level of expertise and training of examiners. SHUTTLE will render analyses more objective and scientific. Second, microtrace evidence analyses are time consuming and hence expensive. This limits the number of cases in which analyses can be carried out.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>SHUTTLE (Scientific High-throughput and Unified Toolkit for Trace analysis by forensic Laboratories in Europe) is a project that developed a tool of great importance for LEAs since it addresses a previously unaddressed need for 24/7 high-throughput screening of forensic micro trace evidence. Similarly, the need for efficient, innovative, user-friendly fighting cybercrime solutions for LEAs is evident and assessed by the CYCLOPES project. Specifically, CYCLOPES is building a database with tools that will consist of a list of novel tools helping LEAs in fighting cybercrime. Thus, SHUTTLE and CYCLOPES are sharing a common target market and network of solution users and thus can be used as an example to follow for innovation uptake.</p>			

6.5. SAYSO

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
<p>Standardisation of situational Awareness sYstems to Strengthen Operations in civil protection</p>		<p>-</p>	<p>1 May 2017 – 30 April 2019</p>
Objective			
<p>SAYSO will address these shortcomings and pave the way for the development of innovative European cost-effective Multi-Stakeholders SA Systems (MSSAS) which will provide practitioners with user-friendly solutions, providing a clear picture of the situation at hand with relevant advices. Addressing both the technical and human aspects of technology implementation, SAYSO will define the specifications of future MSSAS on the basis of practitioners’ requirements and specify the corresponding Reference Architecture to support the integration of various data into a common operational picture. This architecture will support interoperability and allow the integration of legacy and future SAS. It will also be customisable to practitioners’ needs and safeguard adequate privacy protection and data security levels.</p> <p>Moreover, SAYSO will pursue the agreement and sustainable involvement of a community of practitioners, relevant suppliers and potential procurers, institutions and policy makers to obtain widely accepted results and prepare future procurement actions at EU level. SAYSO will also develop a toolkit for MSSAS procurers, which will include tender documentation for SAYSO-compliant MSSAS and a SAYSO Procurers Handbook (with tools to evaluate MSSAS tenders and assess their compliance with the SAYSO specifications and existing standards). A registry of potential suppliers and procurers of MSSAS will be set up. Finally, SAYSO will deliver roadmaps for future MSSAS and standardisation.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>SAYSO (Standardisation of situational Awareness sYstems to Strengthen Operations in civil protection) has developed three platforms: Firstly, a community crisis management library platform that contains common symbols, reference information and documents, and could be used by any emergency responder, practitioner or those with a relevant interest. Secondly, SAYSO has built an active Network and Community called SA-IN-EU, comprising of practitioners, procurers and technology providers. Finally, SAYSO is building Governance Body that comprises of practitioners, suppliers, procurers and representatives of organisations that have adopted the SAYSO specifications and have been tasked to maintain and ensure the continuity of the MSSAS (Multi-Stakeholders SA Systems) specifications as well as the MSSAS development and the standardisation roadmaps. CYCLOPES can follow this example in order to build networks and community and governance bodies that will not only allow innovative solution uptake but also continuity of innovation uptake in regards to solution for LEAs.</p>			

6.6. I-LEAD

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Innovation - Law Enforcement Agencies Dialogue		https://i-lead.eu/	1 September 2017 – 28 February 2023
Objective			
<p>I-LEAD’s focus is on the incapability of groups of operational Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA) practitioners defining their needs for innovation. This will be done in a methodological way, also with the help of the research & industrial partners supplemented by a broad range of committed stakeholders. I-LEAD will build the capacity to monitor the security research and technology market in order to ensure a better matching and uptake of innovations by law enforcement agencies with the overarching aim to make it a sustainable Pan-European LEA network. Earlier funded European research with a high technology readiness level as well as pipeline technologies will be closely monitored and assessed on its usefulness. Where possible a direct uptake from this research will be facilitated and implemented in the ENLETS and ENFSI networks supporting the action. I-LEAD will indicate priorities in five practitioner groups as well as aspects that needs (more) standardization and formulate recommendations how to incorporate these in procedures. As a final step, I-LEAD will advise the Member States through the existing EDBP-ESTP procurement group about how the outcomes of this project could be used in Pre-Commercial Procurement and Public Procurement of Innovation activities.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>i-LEAD (Innovation - Law Enforcement Agencies Dialogue) is a project focusing on the same topic as CYCLOPES Pan-European networks of practitioners and other actors in the field of security ((H2020-SU-SEC-2020 / SU-GM01-2018-2019-2020). Both projects are dealing with LEAs needs in integrating new and innovative tools in their everyday workflow, however i-LEAD is finishing and the lesson learned regarding innovation uptake, can be used for CYCLOPES. I-LEAD – which is another network of practitioners, in one of the tasks also gathers LEA procurement experts, therefore, i-LEAD experience might be very useful for CYCLOPES task 4.4.</p> <p>i-LEADs can provide information and reveal the LEAs with innovation uptake capacity and experience at national and European level, for any technology strategies in place that have the potential to assist in the shaping future applications and innovative use of technology. Thus, we can use such lists as a great base for innovation uptake strategy for Cybersecurity tools during CYCLOPES as well.</p>			

6.7. PREVENT

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
PRocurEments of innoVativE, advaNced systems to support security in public Transport		https://prevent-project.eng.it/	1 May 2019 – 31 July 2020
Objective			
<p>The project will apply six common security scenarios that capture threats and vulnerabilities. The project will create an interactive online instrument aiming at the identification of a 'Common Challenge'. This 'Common Challenge' will serve as the basis for an advanced security system entirely compatible with the EU's privacy and data protection rules.</p> <p>Project aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analyse the existing processes and practices in public transport infrastructures (existing technologies, legal regulation, etc.); • analyse and assess the threats and the vulnerabilities; • build the scenarios through use cases highlighting the gaps between the existing and what would be needed; • analyse the technologies in order to address the process and solutions gaps; • analyse the data protection, legal and economic aspects of the technologies; • determine the overall need and prioritise it, to prepare one Pre-Commercial Procurement. 			
<p>Relevance to Cyclopes Project</p> <p>PREVENT (Procurements Of Innovative, Advanced Systems To Support Security In Public Transport) is a project that has been finalized, however, it is tied to the CYCLOPES project as it provides a foundation on which it can build upon or use as a case study to identify lessons learned. Both projects handle innovations that are analysed and prioritized by practitioners to define challenges, gaps and next steps. Interestingly, PREVENT is based on a sub-subsequent Pre-Commercial Procurement, for which the buyers' group is created, the lead buyer is selected, and tender documents are generated. This methodology can be assessed in the CYCLOPES Project, perhaps integrated and shaped to fit the aims of the CYCLOPES Project. In any case, it provides an interesting point of view that should at minimum be considered with benefits such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PREVENT implements a progressive and iterative process to Scenarios that capture threats and vulnerabilities • It also delivers a vulnerabilities and threats taxonomy • PREVENT undertakes a gap analysis between available solutions, existing standards, on-going research and identified needs, from which it elaborates a multi-dimensional roadmap of innovations and solutions. <p>The above-mentioned benefits and ways of working could be of use to the CYCLOPES PROJECT's aims. Specifically, CYCLOPES is organizing workshops in order to understand the gaps and come up with a taxonomy of the tools that can be used for LEA's that can address the vulnerabilities, gaps and bottlenecks in an attempt to discover innovative ways and solutions to tackle cybercrime.</p>			

6.8. PREVENT PCP

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
<p>PRocurEments of innoVativE, advaNced systems to support security in public Transport – Pre-Commercial Procurement</p>		<p>https://prevent-pcp.eu/</p>	<p>1 September 2021 – 31 August 2024</p>
Objective			
<p>The global aim of PREVENT Pre-Commercial Procurement is to augment the security in public transport through innovative procurement of technology solutions. The proposed technologies will endow Public Transport Operators with solutions enhancing security situational awareness through:</p> <p>i) Timely automatic detection of potentially dangerous unattended items in Public Transport Infrastructure and in public areas in the vicinity; ii) Identification and tracking of perpetrators; and iii) Advanced crisis management system.</p> <p>The PREVENT PCP project builds on the outcomes of its predecessor PREVENT, and it continues the top-down approach that allowed consolidating commonly agreed scenarios, covering the critical security issues down to a detailed identification of the complete set of innovation needs, both at process and technology levels, to ease coordination across the full chain of stakeholders, from transport operators to security forces and public authorities. Therefore, the need for innovative solutions stems from a longer collaboration and is driven by commonly identified internal needs to improve the quality and efficiency of pre-empting terrorist attacks. The project will conduct a phased Pre-Commercial Procurement composed of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: To finalise the tendering documents package already prepared under PREVENT CAS; • Phase 2: To implement the call for tenders for research and development services; • Phase 3: To conduct the competitive development of the prototypes following the PCP principles (design stage, integration & technical verification stage and validation in real environment stage); • Phase 4: To consolidate the results of the evaluation of the developed prototypes, extract conclusions and recommendations from the validation process, and to define a clear strategy for the further uptake of solutions. <p>PREVENT PCP involve 13 public buyers coming from 6 different EU countries and will validate 2 different prototypes in 4 pilots: France, Spain, Portugal and Greece.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>PREVENT PCP (PRocurEments of innoVativE, advaNced systems to support security in public Transport) aims to stimulate innovation and moreover provide a case study “PREVENT CSA” for the first stage of the innovation procurement process. This case study is of interest to CYCLOPES as it provides the means for partners to cooperate in the needs analysis and assessment and the</p>			

procedure by deciding together a Common Challenge. Although the topics of the projects are very different; the methodology used in PREVENT PCP could have value for CYCLOPES, especially the decision-making process of the partners regarding what the desired technology should be able to do and its desirable or mandatory characteristics in order to leave room to industry for innovation.

6.9. iProcureSecurity

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Strategic Partnership of Emergency Medical Service Practitioners for Coordination of Innovation Procurement		https://project.iprocuresecurity.eu/	1 May 2019 – 31 December 2020
Objective			
<p>iProcureSecurity aims at creating a Pan-European Network of medical emergency teams together with medical associations, research and innovation providers, medicine-related media and other relevant stakeholders in order to identify and tackle capability gaps and innovation needs to foster greater involvement of stakeholders in innovation procurement.</p> <p>The iProcureSecurity project will assess the innovation needs and deliver a list of technical requirements for innovative technologies and capabilities that can act as ready-to-use tender documents for a PCP action. However, the aim of the project is to go beyond this mere purpose and establish a network of stakeholders that remain continuously engaged in knowledge exchange also after the end of the project via the Community of Practice.</p> <p>The online community of practice (also known as virtual community of practice) will include active members in a specific area of interest for the project. The online space developed by iProcureSecurity will enable practitioners to create a cooperation mechanism that is long-standing and can enable continuous knowledge sharing in all aspects of their work.</p>			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			

iProcureSecurity (Strategic Partnership of Emergency Medical Service Practitioners for Coordination of Innovation Procurement) emphasizes that every country in the European Union has its own emergency medical services system (EMSS) and when an emergency strikes, Europeans count on these systems to respond with timely and high-quality care. However, there is no common European system and professional standards, organisational structures and coordination mechanisms vary widely across EU Member States.

Similarly, the CYCLOPES Project aims to connect officers to work together, drawing on the strengths of specific LEAs and institutions operating within the cyber ecosystem that require more standardisation for areas related to fighting cybercrime. This refers to certification or accreditation of laboratories and/or tools, standardisation of investigation processes, training, collecting and securing digital evidence, etc. Although the project topics vary greatly, both projects deal with the same challenge of not having one common action plan (that addresses, legislative, technical and cultural barriers) that is the same for all EU Member States.

6.10. iProcureSecurity PCP

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Pre-Commercial Procurement of Innovative Triage Management Systems Strengthening Resilience and Interoperability of Emergency Medical Services		https://pcp.iprocuresecurity.eu/	1 September 2021 – 31 August 2024
Objective			
<p>For the iProcureSecurity procurers, the key common challenges which were identified and discussed during the iProcureSecurity CSA project can be summarised as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick and accurate overview of casualties and their status. • Decision support for better allocation of available resources & quicker support for casualties • Improved interoperability with other first responders and relevant actors. • Reduced handover times between ambulance transport and hospitals. • Insights for quality assurance and training measures. <p>The triage management system is the core component for digitalisation, as it has the vital role of receiving data from the involved endpoints (sensors, services, applications), complements it with contextual data and distributes it to downstream systems, while providing information to decision makers on- and off-site to support the management of the incident situation</p>			

Relevance to Cyclopes Project

PCP iProcureSecurity (Pre-Commercial Procurement of Innovative Triage Management Systems Strengthening Resilience and Interoperability of Emergency Medical Services) is the continuation of iProcureSecurity (CSA) project where a large number of EMS were involved to identify, evaluate and prioritise future challenges and needs. PCP iProcureSecurity follows the EC Guidelines on Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and one of its advantages is that it highlights the Benefits of Pre-Commercial Procurement. The advantage of the PCP is the articulation of a clear technological demand to fill these gaps from a buyers' perspective, which provides industry companies, research institutes and SMEs a detailed insight into the challenges, requirements and operational routines to consider in their R&D and product development, but also to understand the size and potential of the business market they are addressing. This is directly related to the work that will be conducted within the CYCLOPES project with similar challenges arising in both projects.

6.11. iProcureNet

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
Innovation by developing a European Procurer Networking for security research services		https://www.iprocurenet.eu/	1 May 2019 – 30 April 2024

Objective

iProcureNet aims to create an ecosystem of procurers, prescribers, legal advisors and other key stakeholders of security procurement, to share procurement trends and needs, and open pathways for joint procurement.

In an innovative three-cycle process, iProcureNet will map the European procurement environment, compare national investment strategies, identify innovation needs, and analyse security markets.

Security procurement practitioners as well as experts from academy and industry contribute to the development of common and standardised joint procurement practices and innovative approaches, and thus prepare a larger uptake and a common European security market.

Relevance to Cyclopes Project

i-ProcureNet (Innovation by developing a European Procurer Networking for security research services) is similar to CYCLOPES, as they are both networks of practitioners, involved in the area of security. Accordingly, CYCLOPES could gather procurement experts based on i-ProcureNet Network. CYCLOPES is planning to work closely with i-ProcureNet in following years on task 4.4.

6.12. procure2innovate

Name of the project	Logotype	Website	Start date - End date
European network of competence centers for innovation procurement		https://procure2innovate.eu/home/	1 January 2018 – 31 December 2021
Objective			
<p>The Procure2Innovate project will improve institutional support for public procurers purchasing information and communication technologies (ICT), as well as acquiring products and services from a range of sectors that implement innovation procurement. The project has also established a P2I Network to further disseminate its knowledge and attract new members after the project's end.</p> <p>Funded by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Procure2Innovate will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a permanent network of competence centres that will facilitate knowledge sharing, collaboration and the exchange of best practices. • Support (at least) five existing innovation procurement competence centres to enlarge their scope, increase their impact, and enhance their services for public procurers. • Establish five new innovation procurement competence centres, helping them to support public procurers as they become ever more established and experienced in the field. • Spur mainstreaming PCP and PPI across Europe • Support all competence centres to develop expertise in cross-border co-operation and joint procurement. • Communicate and disseminate the tools and approaches (and results) developed by Procure2Innovate competence centres at a European level. This is key to making innovation procurement knowledge accessible to more public procurers and other stakeholders. 			
Relevance to Cyclopes Project			
<p>Procure2Innovate (European network of competence centres for innovation procurement) project will improve institutional support for public procurers of information and communication technologies (ICT) and other sectors that implement innovation procurement. The project will establish or expand competence centres for innovation procurement in 10 European Union countries. As the Procure2Innovate network develops, the approaches to innovation procurement across Europe will become harmonised, with more modern and effective services being offered to public procurers in EU countries. This dynamic is crucial because it means that fragmented public services will be targeted - public services such as healthcare, public work and public transport that are all key to supporting innovation in our societies. Although this project doesn't include the area of Cybercrime it does have valuable information and extensive research on the area of procurement whether it is about innovation procurement, precommercial procurement, and public procurement, cross border procurement and has put efforts into creating a competence centre for innovation uptake based on i procurement procedures. Similarly, CYCLOPES could be inspired by this idea to establish a competence centre as an organisational structure, assigned by its government and with a mandate according to national law to offer technological solutions against Cybercrime and encourage financial</p>			

assistance to public procurers in the preparation and/or implementation of PCP and PPI across all sectors of public interest.

To provide high-quality support to European innovators, researchers, businesses, and consumers, the European Commission established **European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)** [9] with the aim to reinforce the European Union's position as a global leader in Research and Innovation, strengthen its Single Market, open up opportunities for SMEs and maintain high standards of protection for its citizens towards a more competitive, digital, green and inclusive EU.

In December 2013 the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union adopted the EU Programme for the **Competitiveness of Enterprises and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (COSME)**. COSME aims at strengthening the competitiveness and sustainability of the Union's enterprises, particularly SMEs and encouraging entrepreneurial culture and promoting the creation and growth of SMEs.

EU Member States and their regions can also co-finance innovation procurements, including pre-commercial procurements, from the **European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)** [10] in the context of their smart specialisation strategies.

The **European Assistance for Innovation Procurement (EAFIP)** initiative supports public procurers across Europe in developing and implementing innovation procurement. The aim of the EAFIP-initiative is to promote good practices and reinforce the evidence base on completed innovation procurements across Europe as well as to encourage other public procurers to start new PCP and PPI procurements and to boost the digital-green economy recovery through Innovation Procurement (PCP & PPI).

7. Timeline Action in Cyclopes Project

This document is constantly updated and adjusted and published annually as shown in the timeline below.

Figure 3 Timeline of Innovation Reports

8. Conclusion

Addressing the current and emerging economic, social, environmental and technological challenges requires novel ideas, innovative approaches and greater levels of multilateral cooperation. Innovation and digitalisation are playing an increasingly important role in virtually all sectors and in the daily lives of citizens around the world. In the area of security, new technology approaches, and ideas are continually being developed. Across Europe, police and law enforcement agencies are leading the charge, experimenting with new ideas, reacting to changing circumstances, and incorporating feedback from officers and community partners. Emerging technologies that support new notions of operations, enabling the interventions and interactions that keep society safe, are at the heart of the innovations that are changing the future of law enforcement.

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